

editage

Editing Certificate

This document certifies that the manuscript listed below has been edited to ensure language and grammar accuracy and is error free in these aspects. The edit was performed by professional editors at Editage, a division of Cactus Communications. The author's core research ideas were not altered in any way during the editing process. The quality of the edit has been guaranteed, with the assumption that our suggested changes have been accepted and the text has not been further altered without the knowledge of our editors.

MANUSCRIPT TITLE

4-D proteomics method for differentiation of bovine lactoferrin from camel lactoferrin (RT, m/z, intensity, and CCS values)

AUTHORS

Hassan Mohamed Abdalla

ISSUED ON

February 23, 2023

JOB CODE

UAEUN_110

Vikas Narang

Vikas Narang
Chief Operating Officer - Editage

editage

Editage, a brand of Cactus Communications, offers professional English language editing and publication support services to authors engaged in over 1300 areas of research. Through its community of experienced editors, which includes doctors, engineers, published scientists, and researchers with peer review experience, Editage has successfully helped authors get published in internationally reputed journals. Authors who work with Editage are guaranteed excellent language quality and timely delivery.

GLOBAL :
+1(833) 979-0061 | request@editage.com

CHINA :
400-120-3020 或 021-6020-9400 |
fabiao@editage.cn

CACTUS

 IMPACT SCIENCE | impact.science

 RESEARCHER LIFE | researcher.life

 CACTUS | lifesciences.cactusglobal.com